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CHRONICLE

Museum of the History of M.M. Gryshko National Botanical Garden of the NAS of Ukraine from its foundation to the present: concept and development

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Abstract

The prerequisites and concept for creating the Museum of the History of M.M. Gryshko National Botanical Garden of the NAS of Ukraine are highlighted. The names of scientists who contributed to its foundation, from the initial idea to the creation of a temporary exhibition, are provided. The purpose of creating the museum and the target group of future visitors are outlined.

The most valuable museum exhibits are described. It is noted that the primary source of funds for a collection expansion at the museum comes from veterans of the botanical garden and their descendants. Several monographs and numerous articles have already been written based on the museum's collections.

Keywords: M.M. Gryshko National Botanical Garden of the NAS of Ukraine, history, museum, concept

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Introduction

Nowadays, M.M. Gryshko National Botanical Garden of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (NBG) is the leading research institution in Ukraine in the field of plant introduction and acclimatization, and one of the most extensive botanical gardens in the world. The NBG heads the Council of Botanical Gardens, coordinates their activities, prepares scientific personnel specializing in plant introduction and acclimatization, and conducts extensive environmental protection and educational activities. However, the general public still has limited awareness of our institution's scientific activities and historical

development. The creation of a museum of garden history is very relevant, as it will contribute to the preservation of historical documents and the memory of the early stages of the garden's building, as well as the devoted work of its staff, among whom were many distinguished scientists, plant breeders, and remarkable personalities.

Visiting the future museum and becoming acquainted with the work and achievements of their predecessors will also foster patriotic feelings in early careers.

On the museum premises, visitors can watch documentary videos about botanical gardens and nature reserves around the world. Friends and volunteers of the NBG can gather here.

The museum is currently in the developmental stage. The future museum's collections already include hundreds of items: photographs, documents, veterans' personal belongings, commemorative gifts, and other materials.

Results and discussion

Background for creating the museum. The beginning of collection formation

The idea of creating the Museum of the History of NBG emerged in the 1980s. The academician and then director, Andrii Mykhailovych Grodzynsky, was among the first to be interested in the history of the NBG during 1965–1988. He collected literature about V.I. Lipsky and studied his work “The Botanical Garden of the Ukrainian Academy of Sciences in Kyiv” (Lipsky, 1927). A photocopy of this work by Lipsky and materials about him are preserved among Grodzynsky's archives. Grodzynsky also contributed to archaeological excavations of the “Krasnyi Dvir” from the 11th century, the remains of which were discovered on the NBG's territory. He enthusiastically shared his knowledge with colleagues about the history of NBG and the area where it is situated. For the 50th anniversary of the NBG, he authored an article for the anniversary issue of the journal “Introduction and Acclimatization of Plants”, in which he briefly analyzed the functions of botanical gardens and, for the first time, outlined the stages of development of the Central Republican Botanical Garden of the Academy of Sciences of the Ukrainian SSR (now NBG): the pre-war period (1935–1941), the years of occupation (1941–1943), and, in greater detail, the construction of NBG under the leadership of Academician M.M. Gryshko (Grodzynsky, 1986).

Andrii Mykhailovych Grodzynsky instructed the legal advisor of the Botanical Garden, I.P. Dolenko, to determine the real date of the garden's establishment through archival research. Dolenko examined many documents related to the history of the NBG in the State Archive of Kyiv and the Archive of the Presidium of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, and subsequently published a short article. This publication demonstrated for the first time that the NBG at Zvirynets was

founded in September 1935 (Dolenko, 1986). Before that, 1936 had been considered the founding year of the NBG. Dolenko was the first to publish several references to archival documents on the history of the NBG as a subdivision of the Institute of Botany of the Academy of Sciences of the Ukrainian SSR during 1935–1941, thereby greatly facilitating subsequent research work.

In the same anniversary issue of the journal “Introduction and Acclimatization of Plants” from 1986, several other articles are dedicated to the results of the work of individual NBG departments, written by their heads. These publications are valuable sources for studying the history of the NBG.

Owing to these publications, interest in the history of the NBG's creation and development emerged. In the Department of Scientific Information, photographs and documents related to the history of the garden began to be collected. Later, the task of gathering materials for the future museum was entrusted to Doctor of Biological Sciences, Chief Researcher of the Department of Natural Flora, Y.Y. Sikura. The materials he and the staff of the Department of Scientific Information collected are now stored in the museum's collections.

In the early 1990s, Candidate of Biological Sciences V.V. Kvasha actively began collecting photographs and documents for the future museum. In 1999, he involved N.V. Chuvikina (the author of the current paper) in the work dedicated to the history of the NBG. In 2007, she defended her dissertation entitled “The M.M. Gryshko National Botanical Garden of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine: history of its creation, formation, and development” (Chuvikina, 2007) and is currently actively working on the creation of the Museum of the History of the NBG.

The establishment of the museum was greatly facilitated by Tetiana Mykhailivna Cherevchenko, who served as head of the NBG from 1988 to 2004. She was interested in new data about the history of the NBG, the biography of its founder, M.M. Gryshko, and the scientists who worked under his leadership. She also provided space for the museum and storage of collections, and assisted with the creation of six showcases for a small exhibition.

Over the years of working with the museum's materials, we conducted the first

comprehensive and in-depth study of the prerequisites for the establishment and subsequent history of the M.M. Gryshko NBG. New archival documents were introduced into scholarly circulation, along with previously unknown names of leading scientists in the fields of plant introduction, acclimatization, and breeding. A periodization of the development of the NBG was elaborated, identifying the following periods:

- 1918–1935 – the prerequisites for the creation of the academic botanical garden in Kyiv (the ideas of V.I. Lipsky and O.V. Fomin);
- 1935–1941 – the NBG as a subdivision of the Institute of Botany of the Academy of Sciences of the Ukrainian SSR;
- 1941–1944 – the NBG during the period of the Nazi occupation;
- 1944–1964 – the period of active construction of the NBG under the leadership of M.M. Gryshko, the creation of plant collections, and the opening of the NBG for public visits;
- 1965–1988 – the deepening and expansion of fundamental scientific research under the leadership of A.M. Grodzynsky;
- Nowadays – the NBG during the years of independent Ukraine.

Based on this periodization, the structure and concept of the Museum of the History of the NBG were developed (Chuvikina, 2007).

Replenishment of the museum's collection

The primary source of new acquisitions for the museum's collections is donations from veterans of the NBG and their families. Current staff members also contribute to the collection. A significant number of documents, books, and photographs have been donated by the family of the NBG's director from 1944 to 1959, Mykola Mykolayovych Gryshko – from his daughter, Halyna, and son, Yuriy. Some very valuable documents were received from M.M. Gryshko's nephew, Candidate of Agricultural Sciences Borys Kostiantynovych Gryshko-Bohmenko. One of the builders and veterans of the NBG, Ivan Myronovych Shaitan, who dedicated 50 years of his life to the NBG, also contributed to the creation of the museum by donating numerous documents, photographs, and his personal recollections.

The exhibition dedicated to the outstanding landscape architect Leonid Ivanovych Rubtsov is entirely composed of gifts from his daughter, Doctor of Biological Sciences Olena Leonidivna Rubtsova. Many documents were donated by M.M. Gryshko's postgraduate student, later Candidate of Biological Sciences and researcher of the history of biology in Ukraine, Liudmyla Leontiivna Kokhanova. The showcase dedicated to M.F. Kashchenko's Acclimatization Garden, besides the documents provided by I.M. Shaitan, contains materials donated by Kashchenko's granddaughter Maiia Vadymivna Kashchenko, and by the great-granddaughter of M.F. Kashchenko's Acclimatization Garden colleague, Klavdiia Stepanivna Kalachevska. Numerous valuable exhibits have been received from the descendants of the NBG's veterans. The death mask of M.M. Gryshko was presented to the Museum of the History of the NBG by Dmytro Shlionsky, the director of the Museum of One Street. The expansion of the museum's collections continues.

Modern status of the museum

At present, the museum is located in a single large room on the third floor of Laboratory Building No. 2. Since 2002, the museum has been a part of the Landscape Construction Department of the NBG.

The exhibits are arranged in six showcases:

- History of Zvirynets (Fig. 1) – the territory on which the Botanical Garden is currently located;
- M.F. Kashchenko's Acclimatization Garden (Fig. 2);
- Prerequisites for the establishment of an academic botanical garden in Kyiv (Fig. 3) – the ideas of Academicians V.I. Lipsky and O.V. Fomin (1918–1935) and the Botanical Garden as a subdivision of the Institute of Botany of the Academy of Sciences of the Ukrainian SSR (1935–1944);
- M.M. Gryshko (Figs. 4 & 5) – the first post-war director and builder of the Botanical Garden;
- Leonid Ivanovych Rubtsov – eminent landscape architect (Fig. 6);
- Construction of the botanical garden (1944–1964) – photographs, the first scientific collections and guides, personal belongings, and documents of scientists.

Figure 1. Showcase dedicated to the history of the NBG territory, featuring archaeological materials.

Figure 2. Design of the wall above the showcase dedicated to M.F. Kaschenko's Acclimatization Garden.

Figure 3. Showcase presenting materials from the period 1935–1944.

Figure 4. Design of the wall above the showcase dedicated to the first post-war director M.M. Gryshko.

Figure 5. Showcase dedicated to the first post-war director M.M. Gryshko.

Figure 6. Showcase dedicated to the eminent landscape architect L.I. Rubtsov.

Portraits of the directors and prominent scientists of the NBG, who contributed to its design and development are displayed on the walls of the room. The remaining documents and exhibits of the future museum are stored in cabinets. Currently, the museum houses and has cataloged in the accession book 573 items in the main collection and 73 items in the scientific auxiliary collection.

Most valuable exhibits

History of Zvirynets. Archaeological materials – fragments of clay pottery discovered on the territory of the NBG and presented to the museum by the leading researcher of the Dendrology Department, Doctor of Biological Sciences O.M. Gorelov.

M.F. Kashchenko's Acclimatization Garden. A portrait of M.F. Kashchenko with his autograph; publications of the Acclimatization Garden and of M.F. Kashchenko, as well as books and separate offprints of M.F. Kashchenko's articles with his autographs; photographs of M.F. Kashchenko and his family; and inventory lists of the plants in the Acclimatization Garden of 1944 and 1946.

During the Nazi occupation (1941–1943). The director's identification card (Ausweis) of O.M. Burachynskyi, the Botanical Garden's director during the occupation; photographs and documents (work cards and personnel files) of the garden's staff from that period.

Construction of the Central Republican Botanical Garden of the Academy of Sciences of the Ukrainian SSR (1944–1964). A post-war project (40 large photographs mounted in mats (30×40 cm) and a large color panorama painted in watercolor); photographs of the Botanical Garden's territory from 1946–1948; photos from the construction period and photos of the first-generation staff of the Botanical Garden; photographs of the opening of the NBG to visitors on 29 May 1964.

M.M. Gryshko, who was the first post-war director and a developer of the Botanical Garden. Memorial items, monographs, photographs, documents and autographs of M.M. Gryshko, books with his autographs (Fig. 7) and dedicatory inscriptions, books that belonged to him; documents illustrating his friendships with cultural figures (poems and photographs), including an autograph of M.T. Rylskyi (Fig. 8).

Many of the museum's materials have already served as the basis for several monographs and numerous scientific articles dedicated both to the overall history of the Botanical Garden and to the biographies of scientists who worked there during various periods of its development (Chuvikina & Klymenko, 2009; Chuvikina, 2014, 2016, 2021, 2022; Rubtsova & Chuvikina, 2021).

At present, the museum is still under development, which prevents inviting a broad audience. Nevertheless, staff members of the NBG, colleagues from other botanical institutions, and local historians do visit the museum. A visitor log is maintained.

The concept of a museum

A concept has been developed for the future Museum of the History of the NBG, which provides for a significant expansion of the existing exhibition.

In the future, the museum plans to create four large sections:

- General history of the NBG. A significantly expanded version of the current exhibition.
- History of departments and scientific achievements of NBG scientists. For each department, it is planned to have an exhibition stand and a showcase presenting a brief history of the department and its main achievements, portraits and personal belongings of prominent scientists, breeders, doctors of science, award laureates, photographs of some plant varieties; monographs and group photos of staff members etc. Special attention will be given to departments that no exist: the Cytology laboratory, the Department of Plant Physiology, Ecology and Plant resilience, Park studies and Plant protection.
- Information about some interesting exhibitions. This section will present information about some interesting exhibitions held at the NBG over the years (exhibitions by the Department of Floriculture and Ornamental Plants, Plants of the 'Holy Scripture', The Plant World of Taras Shevchenko, and others) as well as gifts to the garden, including paintings, vases, a carpet, and beautifully decorated greeting cards.

Figure 7. M.M. Gryshko's book "Course of Genetics" with his autograph.

Figure 8. Original letter from M.T. Rylsky to M.M. Gryshko.

- Information about the history and activities of the Council of Botanical Gardens and Dendroparks of Ukraine. This section will include information about the Council's work, as well as about some dendroparks ('Sofiyivka', 'Oleksandriya', 'Trostianets', 'Veseli Bokovenky') and historic parks that are monuments of landscape art (Kachanivka, Sokyryntsi, Samchyky, Korsun-Shevchenkivskyy, etc.).

Conclusions

The establishment of the Museum of the History of the M.M. Gryshko National Botanical Garden of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine is essential. The museum's collections already preserve numerous historical documents that recount the initial steps in the garden's construction and the dedicated work of its staff, including

many prominent scientists, breeders, and remarkable personalities.

The documents preserved in the museum's collections serve as a foundation for scientific research and publications.

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Музей історії Національного ботанічного саду імені М.М. Гришка НАН України від заснування до сьогодні: концепція та розвиток

Наталія Чувікіна

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Висвітлено передумови та концепцію створення музею історії Національного ботанічного саду імені Гришка НАН України. Надані імена науковців, які долучилися до його заснування – від ідеї до створення тимчасової експозиції. Окреслено мету створення та коло майбутніх відвідувачів музею.

Описано найбільш цінні експонати музею. Зазначено, що основним джерелом поповнення фондів музею є ветерани ботанічного саду та їх нащадки. Вже нині на базі фондів музею написано кілька монографій та багато статей.

Ключові слова: Національний ботанічний сад імені М.М. Гришка НАН України, історія, музей, концепція